

TEACHERS' MOTIVATIONAL IMPACTS ON SECOND LANGUAGE (L2) LEARNERS' GOAL ATTAINMENT: THE NIGERIAN ESL CONTEXT

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Abstract

In the business of language (L2) learning, it is imponderable to divorce teachers' motivational influence on language learners from learners' goal attainment. Based on the foregoing, this paper attempts a theoretical discourse on the role of language teachers' motivational impacts on second language (L2) learners. Trends on motivational research as it relates to L2 learning, and especially Nigeria's English as second language (ESL) context were reviewed in the light of Self-Determination Theory in L2 Motivation. The theory emphasizes, among other things, the anticipation of 'reward' (intrinsic or extrinsic) as a major determinant of language learning action, as well as 'goal setting' as a dominant factor for analyzing classroom practice in L2 learning. Based on the reviews and the theory applied to them, it was discovered that in the Nigerian ESL context at least, teachers' motivational impact as well as the hope of utilitarian reward, has been long-established sources of L2 learners' motivation. It was also revealed that, though greatly demotivated, with non-provision of incentivized motivation packages, language teachers in Nigeria have continued to produce well-motivated language learners. Thus, it was concluded that there needs to be a sort of balance between motivation for language teachers and expected motivational outputs from them, toward L2 learners' goal attainment.

Keywords: Motivation, Second Language (L2), Self-Determination, Language Learner, Incentives

1 INTRODUCTION

Language learning, unlike language acquisition which is effortless, non-rigorous and fluid, requires the language learner's special study and intentional efforts, (Katzner, 2002, p. 105) some coping potential/abilities, as well as internal (self) and external (teacher-induced) motivation. While language learners draw motivation from the teacher, on the one hand, the teacher, on the other hand requires motivation to enable them teach and motivate the language learners toward an excellent second language (L2) goal attainment.

Motivation, viewed as ‘drive’ in human behaviour (Gass and Selinker, 2008), which view relates directly to *The Oxford English Dictionary* definition of it as ‘a reason or reasons for one’s actions or behaviour’ (2004, p. 587), pervades all spheres of human action or endeavor (Gass and Selinker, 2008; Brown, 2007; Skehan, 1989). Language, especially second language (L2) learning is one such choice actions [a goal] which, according to Dornyei and Kehan (2005), require effort, desire, favourable attitude and persistence – motivation – on the part of the language learner if the goal of language proficiency must be attained.

In the field of foreign or second language (L2) learning, motivation has long been recognized as one of the key factors that determine L2 achievement and attainment. Motivation serves as the initial engine to generate learning and later functions as a driving force for the sustenance of the long and usually laborious journey of acquiring a foreign language (FL). Indeed, it is fair to say that without sufficient motivation, even the brightest learners [of language] are unlikely to persist long enough to attain any really useful language proficiency. Whereas, most learners (especially language learners) with strong motivation can achieve at least working knowledge of L2, regardless of their language aptitude or any undesirable learning conditions. Thus, Gardner (1985) sees the term ‘motivation’ in the context of second language (L2) learning as “referring to the extent to which the individual works or strives to learn the language because of a desire to do so and the satisfaction experienced in this activity” (p. 10).

It follows, therefore, from Gardner’s view that motivation in language learning involves the willingness or even eagerness in an individual (a student) to invest effort in [language] learning activities and to progress therein, in hope of deriving some advantages or reward – a prize, praise, promotion, success in an examination (Brown, 2007) or what Deci cited in Oluikpe & Oluikpe (2014, p. 294) calls “some forms of inner satisfaction”. A motivated learner is thus, one who is willing and/or even eager to invest effort in language learning activities and to progress.

Motivation is an imponderable variable of language – any language. In fact, as Baldeh 1990 asserts, “there have been extravagant claims that the only thing that matters in language learning is motivation (p. 62). In a similar vein, two of the founding fathers of motivation in L2 learning – Gardner and Wallace (1950, 1972) in their seminal work, perceive the L2, as a mediator between different ethno-linguistic communities. Therefore, the motivation to acquire the language of the other L2 community was seen to play a powerful role in promoting or hindering intercultural communication.

In recognition of the profound influence of the L2 learner’s or communities’ attitude and aptitude in their L2 learning, Gardner’s work classified learner’s goal (or

motivation) into two, namely, integrative motivation (orientations) and instrumental motivation (orientations). In integrative language learning, alternatively called intrinsic motivation in self-determination theory, the language learner has a positive attitude toward the target language (TL), its speakers and their culture. He or she is so immensely interested in the language and the culture of the people who speak the language that he/she wants to be integrated into that culture, thus becoming a potential member of that linguistic community (Baldeh 1990, p. 273). Such wish for integration into the L2 culture by the learner may be for immigration or marriage purposes (Brown 2007, p.175).

Instrumental or extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, involves the desire to learn a language in order to fulfill certain utilitarian goals – securing employment, earning higher salary, gaining admission into a tertiary institution, for trade purposes, language training for businessmen or firms’ employees (Ur 2005; Oluikpe & Oluikpe 2014, p. 299). People in this group understandably maintain their language (L1) loyalty and identity. Based upon this background, the next segment of this paper considers motivation in the Nigerian ESL context.

2 MOTIVATION IN THE NIGERIAN ESL CONTEXT

As stated at the outset, language learning, unlike language acquisition is a painfully slow and demanding process, especially where the socio-cultural contexts of the L2 and L1 learners are stunningly different. The language learners’ native habits have been so deeply embedded in them that they inevitably transfer these traits to the system of the target language (TL). This is the experience of the Nigerian ESL learners. In spite of such odds against them however, some illustrations which shall be shown presently demonstrate the fact that language learners in the Nigerian context can succeed, and have actually succeeded in mastering English, a second language, where motivation is high. Sources of such motivation have included the learners’ utilitarian goals, the learning environment as well as an inspiring teacher (Brown 2007, p.175).

In Nigeria, as it were, history has it that the first people to benefit from the study of English were the inhabitants of Badagry, the first point of contact of European missionaries and traders (Daramola, 2005, p. 53). One of the earliest anecdotes of strongest motivation for learning English as reported by Miss Tucker (Tomori, 1977) in a book entitled “*Sunrise within the Tropics*”, is about a Nigeria girl under the guidance of an English Missionary’s Wife: Miss Smith:

...and she had so far mastered the English language so as to be able to read her own verse when a chapter in the English New Testament Bible was read in turn at the morning family worship. Her great ambition was to possess an English Bible, and she worked hard at her lessons [English language lessons] to gain the required proficiency... (p. 150).

What is glaring from Miss Tucker's report above is that the motivating factors in Miss Smith's case were both integrative/intrinsic and instrumental/extrinsic (Oluikpe & Oluikpe 2014, 294). Although research has shown that intrinsic motivation is more powerful than extrinsic orientations, especially for long term retention (Wu 2003; Dornyei, 2001a, 2001b; Noels et al, 2000; Crooks and Schmidt, 1991; Brown 1990), yet other instances of powerful motivation to achieve a near-native, confident ownership of English shall confirm or deny the assertion. Baldeh recounts:

- the children (Nigerian children) were motivated to put in frantic efforts to learn/speak the language of the ruler because it conferred on them the medal of respectability;
- there was the burning desire to read materials written in English especially the Bible (and I believe this was to avoid the kind of situation, as reported in Achebe's *TFA* where the only learned man, defrauded an entire community because only he could read and write letters in English); though of lesser importance then, the desire to be employed as teachers and catechists was cultivated.

At that early times too, Baldeh maintains, the education authorities did everything within their powers to strengthen motivation for learning English in schools and colleges, cognizant of the fact that a good command of the language results in learners expressing their ideas exactly and persuasively (1990, p. 18). In one breath, Baldeh's accounts of motivation of learning English at the early times, give credence to the impacts of learners' effort, intrinsic and instrumental goals as well as teachers' motivational influence on the learners' language goal attainment. The goal of learners expressing their ideas exactly and persuasively" agrees with SP Corder's assertion that:

We (teachers) do not teach language for its own sweet sake.... We (teachers) teach language so that our pupils can communicate and be communicated with, so that they may convey meaning and understand meaning, so that they may enter into satisfactory mutual relations with (other) speakers or writers to the language (1975, p. 30).

Corder's view above is a generalized one, and seems to apply more relevantly in cultures where the English language is used as the L1. In the Nigerian ESL context however, English had, and still has more of utilitarian value – money, prizes, promotion, grades, employment (Brown 2007, p. 172) – than it does the 'integrativeness' in Gardner's model of L2 motivation (Gass and Selinker 2008, p. 427). As such, the language learners' actions are largely extrinsically-motivated actions than they are driven by mere satisfaction for an accomplished self-imposed and self-controlled tasks.

On this matter therefore, Tomori (1977) comments thus: “the motivation for learning English, for being educated, was, and is still to be found employment by others and not to acquire vocation for oneself; not for mere ego satisfaction [emphasis mine]. Education (particularly learning English) was/is thus viewed as a means to an end. It is not surprising therefore that this paper readily identifies with the Annang/Ibibio inspirational school song: “Adá Udo’o kpéb ikó mbakara ke ekama oro edia mkpo’o” (meaning, Udo my good friend learn to use the English language skillfully, because it is the meal ticket of this our era). If the English language is adjudged a meal ticket’ for a skillful learner/user, it therefore follows that the language teacher who deploys the best teaching methods and materials, and whose motivational influence boosts the self-confidence of the motivated learner towards achieving learning outcomes, would have provided the latter with a lifetime meal ticket.

Thus, Naiman *et al.*, the authors of a classic study of successful language, could come to the conclusion that most successful learners of language are not necessarily those to whom language comes very easily; they are those who [through constant tutelage by the teacher] display certain typical characteristics, most of them clearly associated with motivation. The characteristics of a motivated language learner, as identified by the authors include: (a) positive task orientation, (b) ego involvement, (c) high aspirations (d) goal orientation (e) perseverance, and (f) tolerance of ambiguity.

Discourses have shown that the primary motivation for learning English, at least in present-day Nigerian ESL context is more of instrumental/extrinsic than integrative/intrinsic; more utilitarian than for mere self-satisfaction. Viewed in this light therefore, the remarks made by Kellagan (1961) on English language teaching and learning in Nigeria is cogent one. He wrote:

The motivation to learn English in this country is strong, as it is a decided advantage to know the language well. A good knowledge of English opens the door to education, skilled jobs, positions in commercial establishments and the civil service. It is, in fact, often a guarantee of social status (p. 31).

Little wonder then that proficiency in English – at least a minimum score of 75% in the IELTS program – is considered an essential requirement for Nigerians who seek admission or jobs in English-speaking countries abroad. To wrap up this section, the paper recalls Tomori’s report about a survey on the motivation of [Nigerian] adults in Yoruba-speaking communities who wanted to become literate in English in order to:

1. enjoy the pride of a literate person reading to an illiterate;
2. avoid sharing their secrets with the reader; and,
3. be able to write/sign their names (1977, p. 154).

However, among reasons such as practical necessity, economic advantages, status symbol, religious motives and civic responsibilities, for which Nigerians learned English then, Tomori noted that economic advantages had preeminence over others. This has not changed, at least not in any noticeable proportion in the 21st Century Nigeria. If anything, the utilitarian motive attached to English language learning, is even greater. A good grade in the English language is a basic criterion for admission to higher learning locally and internationally; a pass grade in the “Use of English” programme of Nigerian tertiary institutions is “required” before graduation, just as the IELTS certificate is mandatory for admission to universities overseas. Moreover, firms domiciled in Nigeria organize constant training and retraining for certain categories of its staff to enable them communicate effectively at their jobs. And, in every job advertisement seeking applicants, the latter are required to possess good communication skills in English – all these towards utilitarian ends.

For any of the goals of language learning – integrative or utilitarian/ instrumental – to be realized, and for the characteristics of a motivated learner to play out, the teacher (language teacher) is at the core of the matter. On the strength of the foregoing therefore, the next section of this paper will examine motivation for language teachers and language teaching in Nigeria *vis-à-vis* teachers’ role in second language (L2) learning.

3 THEORETICAL BASIS FOR THE DISCOURSE

As there are new paradigms in motivational studies in L2 context, so are there many theories of motivation. Whatever theories there are in L2 motivational research, take their origin from the three major schools of thought – behaviourist, cognitivist and constructivist as categorized in Brown (2007). Based on its suitability however, Self-Determination Theory in L2 Motivation will be adopted as the model for our discourse on teachers’ motivational influence on L2 learners’ goal attainment. The model traces its root to the behaviourist perspective of motivation, in which emphasis is placed on the anticipation of ‘reward’. It holds that people are spurred to do something as a result of the reward they anticipate – a prize, praise, promotion, success in an examination, et cetera. The essence of reward as driving force for any human action underlies the self-determination theory in cognitive psychology. The theory maintains that reward as a driving force, may be intrinsic or extrinsic (Olukpe & Olukpe 2014, p. 294).

Beyond the perspective of reward, it generates (intrinsic or extrinsic), the theory can also be examined from the angle of ‘goal setting’. In this case, goal setting may be intrinsically or extrinsically motivated. Key studies in the area of goal setting in L2 motivation include Noels (2001); Noels, Pelletier, Clement & Vallerand (2000). These studies set out to examine how intrinsic/extrinsic motivation relate to integrative and instrumental orientations in the L2 classroom. The relevance of the

studies to our discourse is in its conclusion that applying the goals setting paradigm is particularly useful in analyzing L2 classroom climate in terms of how controlling or autonomy-supporting it is. This modification supports Brown's (2007) position on how second language learning goals may be set using the intrinsic/extrinsic and instrumental/integrative patterns. Thus there is a consensus on the fact that either the 'reward' or 'goal setting' models could be used to analyze "classroom climate", understood to mean 'the prevailing classroom practice – whether it is the regulatory, traditional method of language teaching or autonomous as in the constructivist-oriented language learning approaches'. Thus, self-determination theory is used in L2 motivational studies for:

- setting second language learning goals
- analyzing the adequacy of second language learning classroom practice using patterns from the theory.

Though of a theoretical nature, this paper finds this theory the most relevant for a discourse on L2 motivation in the Nigerian ESL Context.

4 MOTIVATION FOR LANGUAGE TEACHERS *VIS-À-VIS* TEACHERS' ROLES IN L2 LEARNING

In second language learning (classroom) environment, what undoubtedly influences learners' learning outcome is their interpretation of interpersonal teacher behaviour. So, in language learning, the teacher plays the main role, primarily related to motivation. According to Micky Nasiri, General Manager at Cambridge Silicon Radio:

Although everyone tries one's best, the conditions are different. The obstacles in one's condition could de-motivate the individual, and de-motivated people are normally not successful. A good leader (teacher) works for creating the condition conducive to success for people around him/her (2006, p. 11).

The above quoted source captioned: "*Leader Speech Motivating Leaders...*", shows how leaders in other sectors, and not less so, a good language teacher or facilitator, helps to remove the biggest language learning obstacles from the learners, and create conditions conducive to language learning success. Apart from intrapersonal learner factors such as 'integrativeness', learners (linguistic) intelligence quotient (IQ) (Gardner et al. 2004), language aptitude, as well as the learners' attitude towards the learning situation as shown in Gardner's model of L2 motivation below,

This, the author maintained, was the beginning of payment by results. Also according him, to when in 1882, the education commission compelled mission schools (*The Annual Report of Education Department Southern Providence*) to recruit Irish Fathers for the teaching of English, it was necessary so that they (the mission schools) be awarded the much-needed grant for schools (Tomori 1977, p. 152). It is helpful to note that, the ‘payment by results’ was for the direct benefit of language teachers; hence, a of great motivation for the teaching of language. However, the case of employing Irish Fathers in order to attract grant for schools, was not a direct source of motivation for language teachers, as it had no utilitarian impacts on them.

These attempts at what seemed like motivation for language teachers which, invariably, resulted in well-motivated teachers and better language learning results for the language learners took place in pre-Independence Nigeria. Sadly, though, in post-Independence Nigeria (up till the 21st Century), there has been no record of incentivized motivation for the language teachers; none known to have taken place on a grand scale, except perhaps, those that may be individualized and specific within the contexts of certain language development programmes. The situation, for teachers, [and in the case language teachers] is made worse and even so, more depressing when the annual salaries of other public office holders in Nigeria are compared with that of University professors as seen in the table below:

Table 1: Annual Salaries of Public Office Holders in Nigeria

Public Officers	Annual Salaries (₦)
Senators	36, 677,840.00
Federal House Members	35,932,346.30
Federal High Court Judges	26,874,840.00
Vice Chancellors	22,051,154.30
Local Government Chairman	13,865,895.30
Supervisory Councillors	12,746,875.00
Professors	3,859,078.60

Source: Adopted from ASUU website: www.asuu.com (cited in Odiagbe, S.A. 2012)

If the data shown on the table above, especially as it has to do with professors [some of them, language teachers] can be relied upon with some level of precision, then it follows that the demotivating welfare experience is worse for lower cadres of teachers – language teachers. Despite the huge demotivation – on all fronts – for language teachers in Nigeria, they have continued to motivate the language learners under their tutelage towards attaining their language learning goals. This has resulted in producing effective users of the English language, for instance, whose intelligibility level among other users of English globally have never been in doubt.

Suffice it say that Nigeria's education space abounds with dedicated language teachers, and great motivators who, in spite of their grim demotivating realities, are never disenchanted to the point of losing their motivational influence on their students.

With dedication and constant self-development efforts [most of it self-sponsored], a good number of language teachers in the Nigerian ESL context have made significant contributions to a variety of language teaching and preservation projects. Moreover, the enviable oratory prowess of some Nigerian language teachers, in itself, often provides a great language learning opportunity and motivation for zealous language learners. To begin to x-ray the classroom skills of some Nigerian language teachers may amount to a disservice to some of them, as the right words may not be immediately found to qualify their enlivening classroom sessions, as well as their motivating personalities and influence on the language learners (students).

5 CONCLUSION

In the theoretical discourse on teachers' motivational influence on language learners' goal attainment, the term motivation was discussed, and its types, examined. The concept of motivation as it relates to the Nigerian ESL context was highlighted, with the revelation that English language learning in Nigeria, overtime, has been motivated more by instrumental than integrative goals. Although language learners are usually the prime target of whatever motivational strategies are applied by language teachers, or whatever motivational influence exudes there from, yet this paper dared to expand its scope to touch on what motivational packages have been put in place for the language teachers who, themselves, need motivation in order to produce well motivated language learners. In spite of the many demotivating factors against language teachers in the Nigerian ESL context, the discourse reveals that language teachers, still dispense invaluable motivational influence on language learners under their tutelage. Despite language teachers' strength of character, as so far discussed, this paper inevitably agrees with Mackey's assertion that, "...the more and better the motivation, the better the teaching and learning [of language]". Thus, the paper concludes that there is an inevitable need for better motivation for language teachers in the Nigerian ESL context, as this would reflect on their overall output and enhance their influence on language learners.

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